

**ADDITIONAL COLLECTIONS RECEIVED FROM ARTISANS IN THE
FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKADN KHANATE****Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna,**Associate Professor of the Department of Social Sciences
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Abstract: The article briefly describes the analysis of additional taxes and fees collected from craftsmen operating in the city of Kokand based on archival documents.

Keywords: Craftsman, khanate, fee, service, worker.

Ключевые слова: Мастер, ханство, коллекция, сервис, рабочий.

In the Kokand Khanate, the products made in the workshops of craftsmen were mainly made by hand in hard labor processes. Most workshops were located in the homes of craftsmen, and they were engaged in handicraft work when they were free from farming and other household chores. The main workers were also family members. According to V Akramov, it is difficult to know the exact number of craftsmen working in the city of Kokand. Because the number of craftsmen was recorded by verbally asking elders and market stall heads, especially. Craftsmen and women in home workshops were not included in these figures. In the Kokand Khanate, craftsmen and artisans who lived and made a living in the regions, cities, districts, villages and auls paid zakat to the state once a year. Taking into account the supply and demand in the Khanate markets, artisans often moved from city to city. The book containing zakat data collected from Tashkent in 1868 lists artisans, their origins, and the amounts of money received from them. For example, it is written that 3 rubles were received from the craftsman Mullah Mirabror. Although Tashkent was now part of the Khanate, according to this document, we know that artisans from other parts of the Khanate also sold their products in the Tashkent markets. This notebook even lists the names of craftsmen from Samarkand and the amount of zakat they paid. The artisans sometimes sold their products themselves in the central city markets. The merchants who bought from them delivered them to various countries. In both cases, tax officials collected zakat.

Large amounts of zakat were collected from artisans and merchants to the treasury of the khan or bek. These two sectors developed in close connection with each other.

Since the legal norms of the state in the Kokand Khanate were implemented on the basis of Islam, let us dwell on the Sharia procedure for collecting zakat from artisans and merchants. Zakat is paid on any goods or products purchased for commercial purposes. Zakat is paid in any case, whether this goods are brought to the Kokand Khanate from a foreign country or purchased from a local market. The type of product can be food, cloth, housing, livestock, books, equipment, land, or other things. Zakat is paid regardless of whether the same trade goods are stored in a warehouse, in a person's house or workshop, or in a shop. Even if it is equipment purchased for the purpose of re-production, zakat is paid because it was purchased for commercial purposes.

There is also a specific procedure for calculating the amount of zakat collected from artisans' products and from merchants. As Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf noted: "In both cases, trade goods and other goods purchased for commercial purposes are measured at their market value, and the cash and loans that the person giving the zakat has in his possession and is expected to receive are added to it. If there are debts from others, they are deducted and the remainder is given as zakat.". Zakat is collected from the goods loaded on a camel by a merchant, and the camel is not counted. Zakat is also collected from the profits of a craftsman's products, and his or her labor or capital is not included. When we say capital here, it is understood that the tools and sewing equipment of a craftsman or tailor are not included in the calculation of zakat. If the raw materials that a craftsman receives for the production of a product are stored in a workshop or warehouse for a full year, zakat is collected.

In our opinion, the collection of zakat from artisans in the Kokand Khanate is divided into production and service types based on the nature of their activity. For example, a cloth manufacturer pays zakat based on their investment in raw materials (if they have been in business for a year) and income, while a barber or a cart driver pays zakat based on their income.

In India, the import of valuable goods to Central Asia was mainly carried out by Indian merchants who professed Islam. Because the caravan routes passed through areas inhabited by Muslims, large amounts of customs duties were collected from non-Muslim merchants in these areas. In fact, zakat and toll collection procedures were more expensive for non-Muslim traders.

I. According to Janjul, Muslim merchants were charged 2.5 percent of the total goods, and non-Muslim merchants were charged 5 percent. His information is also presented in the researches of R. Nabiev and H. Bobobekov.

Indians living in the Kokand Khanate actively participated not only in internal trade, but also in trade with neighboring regions. In particular, according to the Tashkent customs records, on March 4, 1867, the Indian merchant Boy Tilla transported 108 rubles worth of Kokand cloth from

Kokand to Tashkent on one horse. In January 1868, Boy Tilla transported 4,800 rubles worth of Russian fabrics from Tashkent to the territory of the Kokand Khanate in 11 carts.

Efremov's notes also contain information that many people from Kashgar, Tashkent, Samarkand, and Bukhara came to Kokand for the purpose of trade. Merchants who came to Kokand were charged a trade tax when crossing the border. If the merchants were allowed to cross the river, they paid money and crossed to the other side. P. Nebolsin notes that "the Bukhara people paid 5 gold coins for a camel of silk fabrics in Kokand. When crossing the river, they paid 40 silver coins for each camel." He also provided information about the procedure for merchants to pay trade zakat when crossing the khanate border. According to him, he heard from the Kyrgyz that Tashkent had left Bukhara and joined the Kokand Khanate, and soon he witnessed the truth of this news. After waiting for the zakat collector for 5 days in Akmasjid to pay taxes from trade caravans, he applied to the chief of the fortress and his affairs were quickly resolved.

The archival documents contain a trade receipt dated March 29, 1869, written in the name of the Jewish merchant Khudoydot Yakh-inia, and according to it, the merchant paid zakat, and the territories of Tashkent, Kattakurgan, and Chirchik are recorded.

Litreture

1. Khatamova, Z. (2021). Expenditure of income from taxes and levies in the Kokand khanate: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In research support center conferences (No. 18.05).
2. Nazirjonovna, KZ (2022). Sh. VOKHIDOV'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects*, 139-141.
3. Khatamova, Z. (2023). Iz istorii denezhnoy politiki v finansovoy systeme Kokanskogo Khanstva. *Aktualnye problemy istorii Uzbekistana*, 1(1), 327–336. izvlecheno noun <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/history-of-uzbekistan/article/view/16511>
4. Nazirjonovna, KZ (2022). Political-Financial Analysis of the Issues of Science of the Khokand khanatein the Work of Khudoyorkhonzade "Anjum At-Tavorikh". *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 3(10), 102-111. Retrieved from <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/463>
5. Burkhonov, IM (2020). "ZAKAT" HAS ENSURED FAIRNESS AND BALANCE IN SOCIETY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 201-204.

6. Muhiddinovich, BI (2020). Negative impact of the tax system on political life-on the example of the history of the Khokand khanate(1850–1865). *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 790-795.
7. Burkhonov, I. (2021). The importance of the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Urinboev in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1242>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).
8. Burkhanov, I. (2023). Nauchnoe nasledie Sharafiddina Ali Yazdi and interpretation Asomiddina Orinboeva. *Aktualnye problemy istorii Uzbekistana*, 1(1), 165–171.
9. BURKHONOV, I. FROM THE HISTORY OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF ABURAZZAK SAMARKAND" MATLA'I SA'DAYN AND MAJMA'I BAHRAIN. *ECONOMICS*, 138-144.
10. Muhiddinovich, BI (2022). The Importance of Asomiddin Urinboev's Scientific Research in the Study of the History of the Kokan Khanate. *Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3, 175-179.
11. Muhiddinovich, BI (2022). In the Study of the History of the Kokand Khanate. *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics*, 6, 68-71.
12. Burkhanov, I. (2022). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE USE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF KOKAND SCIENTISTS ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(10), 63–67.
13. Khatamova, Z. (2021, August). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).
14. Khatamova, Z. N. Osobennosti nalogovoy sistemy Kokandskogo khanstva / Z. N. Khatamova. — Text: neposredstvennyy // *Molodoy uchenyy*. — 2020. — No. 5 (295). — S. 254-256. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/295/66918/>
15. Nazirjonovna, HZ, & Abdumannobovich, NM (2020). Tax system on the territory of Kyrgyzstan during the Kokand Khanate. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 209-212.
16. Khatamova, Z. (2020). Expenditure of state funds replenished by taxes in the history of the Kokand Khanate. *EPR International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 5(3), 274-277.

17. Nazirjonovna, KZ (2024). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ZAKAT IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHAN. *Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 12(3), 100-105.
18. Nazirjonovna, KZ (2024). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHAN: CUSTOMS TAX AND OTHER COLLECTIONS. *Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 12(3), 94-99.
19. Nazirjonovna, KZ (2024). THE ISSUE OF CRAFTSMANSHIP IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 31, 8-10.
20. Burkhanov IA VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV. (2024). *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation* (2995-4827), 2(11), 24-27. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/synergy/article/view/2639>
21. Burkhanov IM (2024). The Significance of A. Urinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14095929>
22. Ilyoskhon Mukhiddinovich Burkhonov, Fergana, teacher at the Central Asian Medical University (CAMU). (2024). REFLECTION OF SOURCES ON THE HISTORY OF THE 14TH-15TH CENTURIES IN AO'RINBAEV'S RESEARCH. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14061206>
23. Khatamova Zumradkhon Nazirjonovna. (2023). THE IMPACT OF THE AMBASSADOR'S PROBLEMS ON THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND-KHANATE: ON THE BASIS OF "ANJUM AT-TAVORIH" OF KHUDYAROKHANZODA. *Fergana State University*, 28(5), 12. Retrieved from <https://journal.fdu.uz/index.php/sjfsu/article/view/2192>
24. Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna. (2024). Important Islamic Sources in Studying the Financial System of the Kokan Khan. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 2(11), 478-481. <https://doi.org/10.5281/>
25. Nazirjonovna, KZ (2024). The Issue of Financing Material-Architectural Culture in the History of the Kokan Khan. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 4(11), 189–193. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejbsos/article/view/4603>
26. Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna. (2024). An Organic Research of the History of the Turkish Nations: A Social Problem in the Financial System of the Kokand Khanate.

American Journal of Political Science and Leadership Studies, 1(7), 30–32. Retrieved from <https://semantjournals.org/index.php/AJPSLS/article/view/505>

27. A VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV. (2024). Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation (2995-4827), 2(11), 24-27. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/synergy/article/view/2639>

The Significance of A. Urinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. (2024). Innovative: International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology (2995-486X), 2(11), 26-28. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/innovative/article/view/2633>